

Research sample of the research on the role of Digital Leadership in bridging the Digital Divide in Education in the period 2015-2025

[Nikolaos Psyrras](#)

University of the Aegean

Department of Preschool Education Sciences and Educational Design

#	1 st Author	Title	Journal	Year	Citations
1.	Agustina, R.	Influence of the principal's digital leadership on the reflective practices of vocational teachers mediated by trust, self efficacy, and work engagement https://doi.org/10.26803/ijlter.19.1.1.2	<i>International Journal of Learning Teaching and Educational Research</i>	2020	23
2.	Akhmad, A.	Digital Leadership Practices in Educational Management: A Narrative Literature Review on Trends and Challenges https://doi.org/10.26803/ijlter.24.8.6	<i>International Journal of Learning Teaching and Educational Research</i>	2025	1
3.	AlAjmi, M.K.	The impact of digital leadership on teachers' technology integration during the COVID-19 pandemic in Kuwait https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2022.101928	<i>International Journal of Educational Research</i>	2022	128
4.	Alenezi (2017)	Technology leadership in Saudi schools https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-016-9477-x	<i>Education and Information Technologies</i>	2017	16
5.	Antonopoulou, H.	Teachers' Digital Leadership and Competencies in Primary Education: A Cross-Sectional Behavioral Study https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci15020215	<i>Education Sciences</i>	2025	6
6.	Baldera, P.R.	Digital Leadership Pioneers: Navigating Outstanding School Principals' Successes in the Evolving Educational Landscape https://doi.org/10.26803/ijlter.24.4.8	<i>International Journal of Learning Teaching and Educational Research</i>	2025	2
7.	Berkovich, I.	Principals' digital transformational leadership, teachers' commitment, and school effectiveness	<i>Education Inquiry</i>	2025	17

<https://doi.org/10.1080/20004508.2023.2173705>

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|-----|-----------------------|---|---|------|----|
| 8. | Berkovich, I. | Principals' digital instructional leadership during the pandemic: Impact on teachers' intrinsic motivation and students' learning
https://doi.org/10.1177/1741143221113411 | <i>Educational Management Administration and Leadership</i> | 2024 | 44 |
| 9. | Clark, F.J. | Future-fit leaders for future-fit schools: Principal narratives of leading rural primary schools for 4IR imperatives
https://doi.org/10.38140/pie.v40i4.6812 | <i>Perspectives in Education</i> | 2022 | 2 |
| 10. | Dasruth, J. | Teachers' perceptions of principals' digital leadership practices in a school district in a developing country
https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssaho.2024.101192 | <i>Social Sciences and Humanities Open</i> | 2024 | 1 |
| 11. | Gallego-Arrufat, M.J. | School technology leadership in a Spanish secondary school: The TEI model
https://doi.org/10.1177/1365480217732232 | <i>Improving Schools</i> | 2017 | 10 |
| 12. | Ghavifekr, S. | Technology leadership in Malaysian schools: The way forward to education 4.0 – ICT utilization and digital transformation
https://doi.org/10.4018/IJABIM.20220701.oa3 | <i>International Journal of Asian Business and Information Management</i> | 2022 | 34 |
| 13. | Gulsen, C. | Teacher views on school administrators' technology leadership competencies | <i>Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology</i> | 2015 | 1 |
| 14. | Hafiza Hamzah, N. | The effects of principals' digital leadership on teachers' digital teaching during the covid-19 pandemic in Malaysia
https://doi.org/10.20448/journal.509.2021.82.216.221 | <i>Journal of Education and E-Learning Research</i> | 2021 | 77 |
| 15. | Hoang, N.H. | E-leadership in the AI era: Exploring Vietnamese EFL teachers' digital leadership development in AI integration
https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-025-13451-6 | <i>Education and Information Technologies</i> | 2025 | 3 |
| 16. | Indra, R. | E-leadership of the school principals in implementing online learning during COVID-19 | <i>Frontiers in Education</i> | 2022 | 3 |

		pandemic at public senior high schools https://doi.org/10.3389/feduc.2022.973274			
17.	Ismail, S.N.	The authority of principals' technology leadership in empowering teachers' self-efficacy towards ict use http://doi.org/10.11591/ijere.v10i3.21816	<i>International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education</i>	2021	25
18.	Jameson, J.	A systematic review and framework for digital leadership research maturity in higher education https://doi.org/10.1016/j.caeo.2022.100115	<i>Computers and Education Open</i>	2022	61
19.	Karakose, T.	Examining teachers' perspectives on school principals' digital leadership roles and technology capabilities during the covid-19 pandemic https://doi.org/10.3390/su132313448	<i>Sustainability Switzerland</i>	2021	201
20.	Muslim, A.Q.	Exploring the Nexus of Digital Leadership and Digital Literacy on Higher Education Performance: The Role of Digital Innovation https://doi.org/10.12973/eu-er.13.1.207	<i>European Journal of Educational Research</i>	2024	12
21.	Nubun, C.C.	Exploring Digital Leadership Competencies among School Administrators and Digital Maturity in Sarawak, Malaysia: From Teachers' Perspectives https://doi.org/10.57239/PJLSS-2024-22.2.00220	<i>Pakistan Journal of Life and Social Sciences</i>	2024	2
22.	Okunlola, J.O.	Principals' Digital Leadership Competencies in the Fourth Industrial Revolution: Teachers' Perspectives https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci15060656	<i>Education Sciences</i>	2025	4
23.	Omar, M.N.	Empowering teacher self-efficacy on ict: How does technology leadership play a role?	<i>Malaysian Online Journal of Educational Management</i>	2021	18
24.	Ping, C.S.	Challenges and barriers to e-leadership participation: Examining the perspectives of Malaysian secondary school teachers https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-023-12206-5	<i>Education and Information Technologies</i>	2024	8

25.	Raman, A.	Principals' Technology Leadership and its effect on teachers' technology integration in 21st century classrooms https://doi.org/10.29333/iji.2019.12428a	<i>International Journal of Instruction</i>	2019	39
26.	Raman, A.	Importance of Technology Leadership for Technology Integration: Gender and Professional Development Perspective https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244019893707	<i>International Journal of Instruction</i>	2019	39
27.	Rasdiana, R.	The effect of digital leadership in nurturing teachers' innovation skills for sustainable technology integration mediated by professional learning communities https://doi.org/10.24294/jipd.v8i10.8480	<i>Journal of Infrastructure Policy and Development</i>	2024	2
28.	Rasdiana, R.	Elevating Teachers' Professional Digital Competence: Synergies of Principals' Instructional E-Supervision, Technology Leadership and Digital Culture for Educational Excellence in Digital-Savvy Era https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci14030266	<i>Education Sciences</i>	2024	25
29.	Shyr, W.J.	Developing the principal technology leadership competency indicators for technical high schools in K-12 in Taiwan https://doi.org/10.12973/eurasia.2017.01215a	<i>Eurasia Journal of Mathematics Science and Technology Education</i>	2017	6
30.	Suharyati, H.	Exploring the role of e-learning, digital leadership and digital innovation behavior on schools' performance during society 5.0 era https://doi.org/10.5267/j.ijdns.2024.5.005	<i>International Journal of Data and Network Science</i>	2024	3
31.	Sujaya, K.	Digital Leadership Competencies to Improve the Quality of High Schools in Tasikmalaya City in the Post-Pandemic Covid-19 https://doi.org/10.14689/ejer.2022.100.015	<i>Eurasian Journal of Educational Research</i>	2022	4

32. Tahir, L.M. Evaluating the Practice of ICT-Based E-Leadership: The Experiences of Private-Based Secondary Teachers *International journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning* 2021 6
<https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v16i23.27437>
33. Tamar, C.L. Digital Leadership: Managing Schools' Virtual Spaces in Times of Crisis *International Journal of Educational Reform* 2023 8
<https://doi.org/10.1177/10567879221142551>
34. Tanucan, J.C.M. Socio-demographic determinants of Filipino school leaders' digital leadership *International Journal of Education and Practice* 2023 8
<https://doi.org/10.18488/61.v11i4.3541>
35. Umah, E.C. Madrasah Principal Digital Leadership Innovation in Digital Learning Transformation *Revista De Gestao Social E Abiental* 2023 9
<https://doi.org/10.24857/rgsa.v17n3-025>
36. Xin, Y. Digital leadership and behavioral adaptation in higher education: Examining teachers' digital competency and teaching performance *Environment and Social Psychology* 2025 1
<https://doi.org/10.59429/esp.v10i11.4229>
37. Yang, Q. Principals' Technology Leadership and Teachers' ICT Integration: A Systematic Review on Capacity Building for Quality Improvement and Sustainable Education *International Journal of Learning Teaching and Educational Research* 2025 1
<https://doi.org/10.26803/ijlter.24.9.11>

38.	Yavuzalp, N.	Technological Leadership of Turkish Secondary School Administrators According to ISTE Standards https://doi.org/10.30828/real.1631148	<i>Research in Educational Administration and Leadership</i>	2025	2
39.	Yuan, F.	Investigating the impact of digital leadership on innovation performance of public universities in Yunnan, China https://doi.org/10.24294/jipd.v8i9.7663	<i>Journal of Infrastructure Policy and Department</i>	2024	7
40.	Yuting, Z.	The relationship between technology leadership and teacher ICT competency in higher education https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-022-11037-0	<i>Education and Information Technologies</i>	2022	38
41.	Zhang, Y.	The relationship between faculty members' perceptions of technology leadership and their technology integration into higher education—Evidence from China https://doi.org/10.1002/berj.4204	<i>British Educational Research Journal</i>	2025	1
42.	Zhong, B.	Effects of Teachers' Technology Leadership on Postgraduate Preservice Teachers' Application of TPACK: Perspective of Path-Goal Theory of Leadership https://doi.org/10.1080/10447318.2024.2400385	<i>International Journal of Human Computer Interaction</i>	2025	2
43.	Zhu, R.	Digital leadership in education: a systematic review https://doi.org/10.11591/edulearn.v19i3.22187	<i>Journal of Education and Learning</i>	2025	3
44.	Zhu, R.	A Threefold Examination of University Digital Leadership, Teacher Digital Competency, and Teacher Technology Behavior for Digital Transformation of Education https://doi.org/10.26803/ijlter.23.10.13	<i>International Journal of Learning Teaching and Educational Research</i>	2024	3
